

THE INSTITUTION AS AN OBSTACLE TO THE SECOND CURVE, AND A POSSIBLE CATALYST FOR IT

My mother, an ambitious and unconformity woman—one of the most dedicated people I know—is now facing financial difficulties. She's always wanted to build something of her own, to have her own business, but that dream has yet to materialize. She separated, moved, and now all the financial costs fall on her, working at what she loves, but with just enough income to cover our needs. Recently, her job hasn't been attracting enough clients, and the economy of our country, Colombia, is worsening. My mother didn't iterate at the right time, when she had more room to take risks, when she was approaching the peak of the first curve and could begin to build her second curve.

I'm currently 22 years old, and my entire life I've lived in a society where risk-taking isn't very common. There's a very distinct culture and social structure where formal education is the most important thing, then getting a job and/or starting your own business... that's where it ends... There's no real outlook that would lead you to consider taking further leaps throughout your life to continue improving and achieving greater success, or at least not too risky leaps. In this country, people tend to settle out of fear. "If something works, don't touch it," they say. This type of thinking directed toward constant innovation isn't commonly taught, neither in homes nor in educational institutions, and to an alarmingly lower degree, in workplaces, where employees are often chosen not to acquire new skills needed in the present and near future. It's vital, not only for individuals but for entire societies, to encourage and make more accessible education geared toward the future of work and the planetary and human needs that must be given close attention. *"The enterprise must be structured to allow people to perform, achieve, and grow."* — Drucker (1954)¹. Institutions, whether governmental, educational, or business, that don't bother to help people grow alongside them are also doomed to fail. One of the worst mistakes here in Colombia is the culture of "the smart guy lives off the fool," which means taking advantage of those who know less or are unprepared. This, coupled with government corruption and violence, only leads to less progress and the country remaining stuck in time.

In Colombia, 5.2% of the population is illiterate². This might not seem like a very high percentage, but this means that most Colombians have basic reading and writing skills; it doesn't mean that education is of quality. The quality of education in Colombia is not good. In Colombia, the percentage of low-performing students is much higher than the OECD average;

¹ Peter F. Drucker, *The Practice of Management* (New York: Harper & Row, 1954), 158.

² Con el encuentro Aprendizajes a lo largo de la vida, experiencias de alfabetización en Colombia, el Ministerio de Educación se une al Día Internacional de la Alfabetización proclamado por Unesco (2021).

<https://www.mineducacion.gov.co/portal/salaprensa/Noticias/406830:Con-el-encuentro-Aprendizajes-a-lo-largo-de-la-vida-experiencias-de-alfabetizacion-en-Colombia-el-Ministerio-de-Educacion-se-une-al-Dia-Internacional-de-la-Alfabetizacion-proclamado-por-Unesco>

71% of young people performed poorly on the 2022 PISA test³. Colombians lack the skills to interpret, read critically, and reason numerically; even teachers lack these abilities. In a country where even basic education isn't good enough, it's very difficult to see people taking a more holistic and forward-looking view. It's inevitable to admit that people live very much in the present and stay in their comfort zone when things are going well; it's scary to take risks, it's scary to lose what you've built, it's scary to pivot; there are no guidelines, no easily accessible information, much less an efficient and effective approach from the entities responsible for providing the best possible services. The government claims that education needs a budget, when it needs more and better-skilled teachers, higher-quality interdisciplinary basic education, a more organized approach to subjects, etc.

I have suffered the consequences of living in a place where short-termism and a lack of innovation and risk abound. It is difficult to build a second curve when the personal and national economic situation is not very stable, nothing is guaranteed, and education was not the best in many respects. *“Knowledge has become the key economic resource and the dominant—and perhaps even the only—source of competitive advantage.”* —Drucker (1993)⁴. Knowledge is the most powerful tool. Well-educated people have little chance of being manipulated; they have the ability to make informed decisions and calculate risks. We can all build a second curve; but it is important to consider the obstacles that exist and how they are perpetuated over the years in different generations.

The two main types of key institutions that have the power to strengthen or weaken our drive to build a second curve:

Government institutions: These types of institutions must safeguard our rights and offer citizens good services and products. It is wrong to exploit them by committing corrupt acts that not only affect the individual but, in the long run, also end up affecting the entire country. We need governments that are also concerned about building second curves, that want to improve the quality of life of their fellow citizens, that address the needs of this new world, and not just rise to power to earn a high salary. It is essential that these institutions:

- Design visionary public policies that foster emerging industries; and establish national plans for innovation and digital transformation.
- Create enabling legal and economic frameworks, such as tax incentives for startups, research, and innovation, and financial support for sectors in transition or reconversion.
- Facilitate infrastructure and connectivity. Invest in digital connectivity, sustainable transportation, and clean energy.
- Promoting ongoing training with public programs to update job skills; and supporting job retraining in sectors affected by automation or climate change.

³El problema de la educación de calidad en Colombia no es solo de recursos, falta estrategia (2024).

<https://periodico.unal.edu.co/articulos/el-problema-de-la-educacion-de-calidad-en-colombia-no-es-solo-de-recursos-falta-estrategia>

⁴ Peter F. Drucker, *Post-Capitalist Society* (New York: HarperBusiness, 1993), 8.

Some of the points mentioned above are being put into practice; however, it is important to avoid the following:

- Governing with a short-term vision.
- Maintaining a rigid bureaucracy.
- Favoring obsolete industries.

Educational institutions: These institutions should primarily be responsible for providing quality service, with well-prepared teachers who motivate and teach their students how to intelligently pivot into the future, providing them with the necessary basic skills to help them identify, reason, critique, and interpret. Therefore, it is essential that these institutions:

- Update curricula for the future, including critical thinking, technology, sustainability, and entrepreneurship; and also integrate interdisciplinary learning.
- Promote applied research and innovation, connecting academia with businesses and governments to solve real challenges; Additionally, create innovation labs and technology transfer centers.
- Train global and adaptable citizens, preparing students for changing environments, not just for current jobs; and develop soft and digital skills.

The ways these institutions would generate negative consequences are as follows:

- Sticking to traditional teaching models.
- Disconnecting from the environment and its needs.
- Reluctance to collaborate with other sectors.

Now, even though these structural changes seem difficult to combat, there are communities fighting to ensure that talent isn't wasted. I know of one called "@personalbranding.pe" on Instagram, which I also volunteer for. They work to ensure Latin Americans have access to higher education opportunities, both nationally and internationally; they also encourage them to train for future employability.

I've also created a small community for people in Latin America (@campuscrafter on Instagram), where I share information related to green skills, climate change, digital literacy, and both national and international educational opportunities. My goal is for young people to understand how to use technological and digital tools optimally, to learn how to search for useful information and avoid falling for fake news or conspiracies. It's also important for them to relate all of this to caring for the planet.

In conclusion, I can say that institutions today are improving their adaptation to this new world, which is increasingly globalized and digitalized. The efforts are noticeable and appreciated; however, much more work must be done on the human factor, not simply doing things for the sake of doing them. It is vital to listen to people and understand their needs. In his book "The Second Curve," Charles Handy wondered if one day what would move people might not be money... And I also wonder if one day the world will care more about human beings than about

material things, because if that were to happen, we would have much kinder societies and, I would like to think, much more technologically advanced ones, without harming the planet, which is another very important factor. However, despite being conditioned by our environment, culture, and opportunities, we must keep Handy's phrase in mind: "*The future is not inevitable. We can influence it if we know what we want it to be.*"⁵ It is essential to know what you want from your life in order to act with determination and achieve that goal you desire. Limitations come and go; we always face obstacles in our path. Resistance to change, attachment to the familiar, institutional inertia, or a lack of long-term vision can hinder the emergence of new ideas. But it's also up to us to know how to overcome them.

Building a second curve is not only an act of organizational or personal survival, but a commitment to transformation; it's a conscious commitment to change before the current model collapses. The key is to anticipate, to imagine new possibilities while there is still stability, resources, and room for maneuver.

⁵ Charles Handy, *The Second Curve* (2015), p. 1